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The quest of Responsible Artificial Intelligence Systems: Trustworthiness and safety

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OUTLINE

Artificial Intelligence : Risk, regulation, trustworthiness, governance

The quest of Responsible AI Systems

Responsible AI Systems. Trustworthy AI challenges

Conclusions

AI: Risk, regulation, trustworthiness, governance

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Toju Duke, exdirectora de IA de Google: “La inteligencia artificial amplifica injusticias sistémicas que ya deberíamos haber eliminado”

La exdirectora de IA responsable en Google cree que el debate sobre esta tecnología se ha centrado en si la humanidad correrá peligro mañana, cuando el problema es que hoy ya discrimina a la población

20 de octubre de 2023 • 16:25

Manuel G. Pascual
EL PAIS

Toju Duke, former responsible AI director at Google: “Artificial intelligence amplifies systemic injustices that we should have already eliminated”

The former director of responsible AI at Google believes that the debate about this technology has focused on whether humanity will be in danger tomorrow, when the problem is that today it already discriminates against the population

AI: Risk, regulation, trustworthiness, governance

Policy paper

The Bletchley Declaration by Countries Attending the AI Safety Summit, 1-2 November 2023

Published 1 November 2023

In the context of our cooperation, and to inform action at the national and international levels, our agenda for addressing frontier AI risk will focus on:

- identifying AI safety risks of shared concern, ...
- building respective risk-based policies across our countries to ensure safety in light of such risks, ...

AI: Risk, regulation, trustworthiness, governance

AI Act: European risk-based scenario

THE AI ACT

INTELIGENCIA ARTIFICIAL >

Una ley pionera para una tecnología con muchos interrogantes : las claves de la regulación de la IA en la UE

Bruselas celebra como un "momento histórico" el acuerdo, que deja dudas sobre su aplicación y el control efectivo a las empresas

Regulatory
european
framework
based on
Risk levels

AI: Risk, regulation, trustworthiness, governance

Trustworthy AI is a systemic approach to develop, deploy and use AI systems with safety and responsibility for (high) risk scenarios (EU AI Act), to design **Responsible AI Systems**

It is a prerequisite for people and societies

EU AI Act: a risk-based approach

AI: Risk, regulation, trustworthiness, governance

Trustworthy AI: REQUIREMENTS (European guidelines)

1. Human agency and oversight
2. Technical robustness and safety
3. Privacy and data governance
4. Transparency
5. Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness
6. Social and environmental well-being
7. Accountability

7 Key Requirements for Trustworthy AI

To be continuously evaluated and addressed throughout the AI system's life cycle

AI: Risk, regulation, trustworthiness, governance

Trustworthy & Responsible AI Resource Center

AI Risk Management Framework

AI RMF The AI Risk Management Framework (AI RMF) is intended for voluntary use and to improve the ability to incorporate trustworthiness considerations into the design, development, use, and evaluation of AI products, services, and systems.

AI RMF

- 1 Framing risk
- 2 Audience
- 3 AI Risks and Trustworthiness
- 4 Effectiveness of the AI RMF
- 5 AI RMF Core
- 6 AI RMF Profiles

AI Risks and Trustworthiness (characteristics)

Approaches which enhance AI trustworthiness can reduce negative AI risks.

Safe

Secure &
Resilient

Explainable &
Interpretable

Privacy-
Enhanced

Fair - With Harmful
Bias Managed

Accountable
&
Transparent

Valid & Reliable

AI: Risk, regulation, trustworthiness, governance

Artificial intelligence governance (AIG) is the **legal framework** for ensuring trustworthy AI technologies are **developed** with the goal of helping humanity navigate the adoption and use of AI systems in **ethics and responsible ways**.

AI governance along the AI Lifecycle aims to close the gap that exists between accountability and ethics in technological AI advancement:

Towards Responsible AI Systems.

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The quest of Responsible Artificial Intelligence Systems: Trustworthy, safe and governable AI

Responsible AI system. “It is an **AI systems** that requires ensuring **auditability and accountability** during its design, development and use, according to specifications and the **applicable regulation** of the domain of practice in which the AI system is to be used.” [Diaz-Rodríguez et al 23].

Responsible AI Systems

We need update the definition, looking for on the principles (now on the obligations)

The quest of Responsible Artificial Intelligence Systems:

Trustworthy, safe and governable AI

AI governance: Auditability and certification

Auditability refers to a **property sought for the AI-based system**, which may require transparency (e.g. explainability methods, traceability), measures to guarantee technical robustness, etc.

The auditability of a “responsible AI system” may not necessarily cover all requirements for trustworthy AI, but rather those foretold by ethics, regulation, specifications and protocol testing **adapted to the application sector** (i.e., vertical regulation).

We need update the definition, looking for on the principles (now on the trustworthy AI requirements)

The quest of Responsible Artificial Intelligence Systems:

Trustworthy, safe and governable AI

The four key stages of algorithm audits

AI governance:
Auditability and
certification

What is AI Auditing?

One among a lot of
approaches/conjectures

The quest of Responsible Artificial Intelligence Systems: Trustworthy, safe and governable AI

Requirements for high-risk AI systems (AI Act, Title III, Chapter 2)

The quest of Responsible Artificial Intelligence Systems: AI safety

Safety and Robustness Example

Jon Henley

@jonhenley

Sun 24 Jul 2022 14:37 CEST

Chess robot grabs and breaks finger of seven-year-old opponent

Moscow incident occurred because child 'violated' safety rules by taking turn too quickly, says official

Chess robot grabs and breaks finger of seven-year-old opponent - video

Played by humans, chess is a game of strategic thinking, calm concentration and patient intellectual endeavour. Violence does not usually come into it. The same, it seems, cannot always be said of machines.

VIDEO

The
Guardian

The quest of Responsible Artificial Intelligence Systems: AI safety

This sweater works as an invisibility cloak against Artificial Intelligence

[VIDEO](#)

Safety and Robustness. Adversarial Attack

A jersey that uses “**adversarial patterns**” that remove the common patterns these systems are trained to, making it invisible to the AI.

The quest of Responsible Artificial Intelligence Systems: AI safety

AI safety is an interdisciplinary field concerned with preventing accidents, misuse, or other harmful consequences that could result from AI systems.

AI safety encompasses

- machine ethics and AI alignment, which aim to make AI systems moral and beneficial, and
- robustness technical problems referred to as the ability of an AI system to maintain its performance against various perturbations and adversarial inputs.

The quest of Responsible Artificial Intelligence Systems: AI safety

Robustness technical problems: Ability of an AI system to maintain its performance against various perturbations and adversarial inputs along the **AI lifecycle**.

Algorithm robustness, to measures how robust the learning algorithm is to changes in the underlying data set;

Model robustness, to quantify a trained model's robustness to input perturbations. Including, monitoring systems, adversarial robustness, detecting malicious use, attacks and backdoors, transparency, ...)

Robustness technical problems, including monitoring systems, adversarial robustness, detecting malicious use, attacks and backdoors, transparency, all aspects on the AI maintenance and the AI system's lifecycle of a successful behavior as it was conceived.

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Responsible AI Systems. Trustworthy AI challenges

Traceability, explainability, and communication (KR4)

Traceability is defined as the set of mechanisms and procedures aimed to keep track of the system's data, development and deployment processes

Explainability

Given an audience, an explainable AI is one that produces details or reasons to make its functioning clear or easy to understand.

Communication is a crucial dimension, so that all aspects related to transparency are delivered to the audience in a form and format adapted to their background and knowledge. This is key to attain trust in the audience about the AI-based system at hand.

Responsible AI Systems. Trustworthy AI challenges

Traceability, explainability, and communication (KR4)

Challenge: Post-hoc explainability approaches

Why are explanations useful?
How to measure explanations?

Benchmarking and survey of explanation methods for black box models

Francesco Bodria¹ · Fosca Giannotti¹ · Riccardo Guidotti³ ·
 Francesca Naretto¹ · Dino Pedreschi³ · Salvatore Rinzivillo²

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Research Article

REVEL Framework to Measure Local Linear Explanations for Black-Box Models: Deep Learning Image Classification Case Study

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Responsible AI Systems. Trustworthy AI challenges

Privacy and data governance (KR3)

Federated Learning

Local update

- Model update strategy
- Personalization
- Versioning

Aggregation delivery

- Encryption protocol
- Communication schedule

Local training

- Client device
- Local model
- Local dataset

Communication

- Encryption protocol
- Communication schedule

Global model

- Aggregator architecture
- Aggregation policy/strategy
- Versioning

Federated learning process and workflow

Responsible AI Systems. Trustworthy AI challenges

Privacy and data governance (KR3)

Use high-quality **training, validation and testing data** (relevant, representative etc.) (AI Act, Title III, Chapter 2)

Data governance

Governance for data trust (creating datasets for AI):

Data provenance, collection & presentation (minimum criteria, origin...), using and sharing data, checklist for dataset conformity

Data maintenance and robustness.

Trusted data, data integrity, data protection

Responsible AI Systems. Trustworthy AI challenges

Data quality and excellence

Data-centric AI

AI Lifecicle

Use high-quality **training, validation and testing data** (relevant, representative etc.) (AI Act, Title III, Chapter 2)

Previous state of the art UGR books: **Data preprocessing and smart data**

Data Excellence for AI:
“garbage in = garbage out”

Sambasivan et al. 2021:
“The only reason machine learning works is because the data contains knowledge, not because the heuristics to extract it are perfect.”

Source: Chen et al. 2023

Responsible AI Systems. Trustworthy AI challenges

Data quality and excellence

Data-centric AI

Use high-quality **training, validation and testing data** (relevant, representative etc.) (AI Act, Title III, Chapter 2)

Data quality

Data-centric AI. It is the discipline of systematically engineering the data to build an AI system. The emphasis is on data quality and creating tools to facilitate building AI solutions with the highest accuracy. Some essentials to discussion:

- **Data quality** needs and practice in selected sectors.
- **Data quality assessment, data preprocessing, and bias mitigation** in research and industry.
- **Data ‘fairness’**, decision making processes based on AI, objectivity and quantitative measures.

Responsible AI Systems. Trustworthy AI challenges

Data quality and excellence

Everyone wants to do the model work, not the data work.

Use high-quality **training, validation and testing data** (relevant, representative etc.) (AI Act, Title III, Chapter 2)

Data quality

The only reason machine learning works is because the data contains knowledge, not because the heuristics to extract it are perfect (as the No Free Lunch theorem demonstrates, for any heuristic there is a data set where it doesn't work!).

It seems that sometimes “we have forgotten” that **the important thing is that the data represents the distribution to be learned**, and this has an at least moderately simple structure, avoiding biases, including corner cases generation, ...

Responsible AI Systems. Trustworthy AI challenges

Data quality and excellence

“garbage in = garbage out”

Use high-quality **training, validation and testing data** (relevant, representative etc.) (AI Act, Title III, Chapter 2)

Data quality

Insights Data Excellence for AI: Why Should You Care?

- Measurement of AI success is often metrics driven and does not tell us much about **data fidelity and validity**. **No standardized metrics exist** yet for characterizing the **goodness-of-data**.
- If “data is the new oil,” our use of data remains crude, and we are missing work on the **refineries** by which the **data itself could be optimized**.
- Real-world datasets are often “**dirty**”, with various data-quality problems and **the risk of “garbage in = garbage out.”**

Garbage in, garbage out: mitigating risks and maximizing benefits of AI in research

Brooks Hanson, Shelley Stall, Joel Cutcher-Gershenfeld, Kristina Vroonwelder, Christopher Wirz, Yuhua (Douglas) Rao & Ge Peng

nature

Artificial-intelligence tools are transforming data-driven science - better ethical standards and more robust data curation are needed to fuel the boom and prevent a bust.

Responsible AI Systems. Trustworthy AI challenges

Robustness and safety (KR2)

AI Lifecycle & robustness inspection

Source: Chen et al. 2023

FIGURE 2. The AI model inspector framework consists of detection and mitigation stages.

Source: Chen et al. 2023

Responsible AI Systems. Trustworthy AI challenges

Robustness and safety (KR2)

AI Lifecycle

Highlighted robustness challenges in the AI lifecycle

AI Lifecycle & robustness inspection

Source: Chen et al. 2023

Source: Chen et al. 2023

Responsible AI Systems. Trustworthy AI challenges

Robustness and safety (KR2)

Source: Chen et al. 2023

Source: Hendrycks et al., 2022

Monitoring

Anomaly Detection

- Warn operators
- Flag novel misuses

Representative Model Outputs

- Calibrate probabilities
- Know when to override

Hidden Functionality

- Find model trojans
- Scan for capabilities

Figure 2: Monitoring research aims to identify hazards, inspect models, and help human ML system operators.

Fig. 1: Taxonomy of generalized OOD detection framework,

Source: Yang et al. 2022

Responsible AI Systems. Trustworthy AI challenges

Secure and resilient

Secure and resilient

AI Risks and Trustworthiness

Security and resilience are related but distinct characteristics.

- **While resilience is the ability to return to normal function after an unexpected adverse event,**
- **security includes resilience but also encompasses protocols to avoid, protect against, respond to, or recover from attacks.**

Resilience relates to robustness and goes beyond the provenance of the data to encompass unexpected or adversarial use (or abuse or misuse) of the model or data.

Responsible AI Systems. Trustworthy AI challenges

Robustness and safety (KR2)

AI Safety

Figure 5: A Swiss cheese model of ML Safety research. Pursuing multiple safety research avenues creates of protection which mitigates hazards and makes ML systems safer.

Unsolved Problems in ML Safety

-
Robustness Create models that are resilient to adversaries, unusual situations, and Black Swan events.
-
Monitoring Detect malicious use, monitor predictions, and discover unexpected model functionality.
-
Alignment Build models that represent and safely optimize hard-to-specify human values.
-
Systemic Safety Use ML to address broader risks to how ML systems are handled, such as cyberattacks.

Source: Hendrycks et al., 2022

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Conclusions: Working on the bridge between

“AI technology versus Ethics and Society's concerns”

Conclusions: 3 challenges for applying Regulation

“Trustworthiness and safety technologies” VS “governance and regulation”

Auditability “desired/sought properties for the AI system”

Certification “fulfill the requirements of agreed-upon responsible AI regulations”

A) What must a responsible AI system accomplish by design (from a technological point of view) in a specific high-risk application?
(Trustworthy technologies vs regulation)

B) How to audit AI systems in currently deployed by companies?
(Auditability after design, consulting and auditing work)

C) How to continually evaluate and address the life cycle of the AI system? (On going after deployment: safe, secure and resilient AI)

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